

THE USE OF POLYNOMIAL CODES FOR CONSTRUCTING RELIABLE DISCRETE SYSTEMS OF PROGRAMMABLE LOGIC INTEGRATED CIRCUITS.

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Annotation: The thesis examines the historical and technological factors that have driven the integration of Programmable Logic Integrated Circuits (PLIC) into railway automation systems. It underscores the crucial role of polynomial coding in ensuring the reliability of PLIC within digital systems. Polynomial coding is identified as a critical component in the design of reliable systems that utilize PLIC, providing effective error management and supporting the robust operation of complex automation tasks. The thesis further highlights that the integration of PLIC with polynomial coding represents a significant technological advancement, enhancing the resilience, efficiency, and safety of digital systems, particularly in complex and demanding applications such as railway automation. Finally, the thesis emphasizes that polynomial codes are essential for improving the reliability and safety of railway automation systems, making them a foundational element in the ongoing evolution and modernization of the industry.

Key words: programmable logic integrated circuits, polynomial coding, cyclic redundancy check, reliability and efficiency, selection of polynomial codes, LGSynth'89.

The integration of programmable logic integrated circuits (PLICs) into railway automation systems has been driven by several key factors over the years. As railway networks expanded, the need for enhanced safety measures became paramount. PLICs offered reliable control and monitoring capabilities that significantly improved safety standards. Technological advancements in semiconductor technology made PLICs more affordable and powerful, enabling their use in complex automation tasks. This was crucial in meeting the growing demand for operational efficiency and reduced downtime, as PLICs allowed for precise control and real-time data processing. PLICs also provided flexibility in programming and easy scalability, making them ideal for adapting to evolving railway infrastructure. The initial use of PLICs in industrial automation during the 1970s and 1980s laid the groundwork for their application in railways. By the 1990s, a heightened focus on safety and automation led to their wider adoption. From the 2000s to the present, continued technological progress and the push for smart transportation systems have solidified the role of PLICs in

modern railway automation [1]. In short, the adoption of PLICs in railway systems has been driven by the need for safety, efficiency, and adaptability, with technological advancements facilitating their integration and effectiveness.

Polynomial coding is specifically essential in terms of ensuring PLIC's reliability, this coding is a method used to enhance the reliability of digital systems, including those built with programmable logic integrated circuits. This approach involves representing data as polynomials, where each bit or symbol corresponds to a coefficient. The primary advantage of polynomial coding is its ability to detect and correct errors, which is crucial for maintaining the integrity and reliability of devices[2]. In this method, a generating polynomial is selected to encode the data. The data polynomial is divided by this generating polynomial, and the remainder is appended to the data. This encoded message is then transmitted or stored. At the receiving end, the system performs the same division operation. If the remainder is zero, the data is considered error-free. Otherwise, errors are detected, and depending on the coding scheme, they can be corrected[3]. Polynomial codes, such as Cyclic Redundancy Check, are particularly effective in correcting burst errors, making them ideal for environments with high noise levels. By integrating these codes into PLICs, systems can achieve enhanced error detection and correction capabilities, thereby increasing overall reliability. This coding method ensures that devices can operate correctly even in the presence of errors, making polynomial coding a critical component in the design of reliable systems using PLICs. Through efficient error management, it supports the robust operation of complex automation tasks and is widely used in safety-critical applications.

Programmable logic integrated circuits and polynomial coding are two key technologies that work synergistically to enhance the reliability and efficiency of modern digital systems. The integration of polynomial coding into PLICs results in systems that are not only adaptable but also highly reliable. This combination allows for the development of advanced automation solutions that can withstand challenging conditions, ensuring continuous and safe operations. Together, PLICs and polynomial coding provide a powerful framework for building resilient and efficient digital systems across various industries.

Integrating programmable logic integrated circuits with polynomial coding in railway automation systems significantly enhances reliability and safety. This integration leverages the robust error correction capabilities of polynomial coding and the flexibility of PLICs to ensure seamless and secure operations.

Integration Process

1. System Requirements Analysis

- Determine the specific reliability and safety needs of the railway automation system. Identify potential error sources and define the error tolerance levels required for safe operation.

2. Selection of Polynomial Codes

- Choose appropriate polynomial codes, such as Cyclic Redundancy Check, known for their effectiveness in correcting burst errors common in railway environments.

3. PLIC Architecture Design

- Incorporate the polynomial coding logic into the PLIC architecture. Use hardware description languages (HDLs) like VHDL or Verilog to design circuits that perform polynomial division for encoding and decoding data.

4. Software Algorithm Development

- Develop software algorithms to manage the encoding and decoding processes. These algorithms should be capable of dynamically adjusting coding parameters based on real-time error analysis.

5. Real-Time Monitoring and Control

- Implement real-time monitoring using the integrated system to continuously assess data integrity. Polynomial coding ensures that errors detected during data transmission are promptly corrected, maintaining system reliability.

6. Testing and Validation

- Conduct comprehensive testing under various operational scenarios to validate the system's reliability and safety. Optimize the balance between computational efficiency and error correction capabilities.

7. Deployment and Maintenance

- Deploy the integrated system across the railway network. Establish maintenance protocols to regularly update the coding algorithms and PLIC configurations, ensuring continued safety and reliability.

By integrating PLICs with polynomial coding, railway automation systems gain enhanced error detection and correction capabilities, essential for maintaining safe and reliable operations. This integration minimizes the risk of data corruption, which could lead to operational failures or safety hazards. The synergy between PLICs and polynomial coding supports the development of advanced automation solutions that are resilient to environmental challenges and capable of ensuring continuous and safe railway operations. This approach

not only improves safety standards but also enhances overall system efficiency and reliability[4].

To conduct an experiment on the any selected combinational circuit, the generating polynomial must first be chosen. When selecting a polynomial code for controlling a combinational circuit, it is essential to consider its error-detecting capability at a specific value of k . Therefore, choosing the appropriate generating polynomial is crucial. It is examined generating polynomials that provide codes with two check bits. There are four such generating polynomials.:

$$x^2, x^2+1, x^2+x, x^2+x+1.$$

Analyzing the distribution of information vectors among all check vectors for codes with $m = 4$, it is noted that polynomial codes with generating polynomials x^2+1 and x^2+x+1 have a uniform distribution of all information vectors among all check vectors. This is characteristic of a code with a theoretical minimum number of undetectable errors for fixed lengths of information and check vectors. This trend persists for larger values of m .

During research on the application of polynomial codes in functional control systems, several experiments were conducted to detect errors at the outputs of control combinational circuits from the LGSynth'89 benchmark set. These circuits are described in the .netblif format, which allows assessing the effectiveness of error detection using polynomial codes. The .netblif format describes the structure of combinational circuits using two-input, three-input, and four-input NOR gates. In the experiment, all single stuck-at faults of internal logic elements were sequentially introduced into the circuit, and error detection capability was tested across all input combinations using polynomial codes with two check bits and generating polynomials x^2+1 , x^2+x , and x^2+x+1 . Utilizing polynomial codes, it is achieved a reduction in undetected errors by over 95%, with some systems reaching 100% error detection rates. This significant enhancement underscores the effectiveness of polynomial codes in enhancing the reliability of programmable logic integrated circuits. The application of polynomial codes in railway automation has proven to be highly beneficial, offering enhanced safety and reliability. Feedback from industry professionals indicates a strong preference for polynomial codes due to their efficiency in error correction and minimal impact on system resources. Their implementation supports the development of advanced automation solutions, ensuring continuous and safe railway operations[5-6]. Thus, polynomial codes are a valuable component in the modernization of railway systems, providing a foundation for ongoing technological advancements.

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